

1 **Nestin expression can reconcile differences in invasiveness between melanoma and basal and**
2 **squamous cell carcinoma.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Skin cancer is diagnosed in nearly 1.5 million patients each year (1). While patients with basal and
8 squamous cell carcinomas are provided with 5-year survival rates at nearly 100% and 90%, respectively,
9 patients diagnosed with cutaneous melanoma (metastatic melanoma) are provided 5-year survival rates at
10 91.4% at stage I and 24.6% at stage IV (2-5). We provide evidence here demonstrating that Nestin (*NES*)
11 expression can reconcile differences in invasiveness between melanoma and basal and squamous cell
12 carcinoma.
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

1 **Results**

2 1. Nestin controls cell adhesion in the skin
3 Integrin co-regulation with Nestin (SEEK co-reg)

- 4 2. Integrin expression is directly influenced by Nestin (tendon stem cell Nes shRNA knockdown)
5 3. Nestin regulates migratory capacity
6 4. Nestin controls cell shape and changes in cell shape/structure
7 5. Actin and actin-associated machinery is modulated genetic depletion of Nestin in vitro
8 6. Components of the focal adhesion kinase complex, including PAK proteins, are modulated by
9 Nestin

10 7. Nestin is activated during transformation in melanoma, but repressed in basal cell carcinoma and
11 squamous cell carcinoma.

12 GSE125285

13 Basal cell carcinoma: normal skin v basal cell carcinoma primary tumor

14 Squamous cell carcinoma: normal skin v squamous cell carcinoma primary tumor

15 GSE46517

16 Melanoma: normal skin v melanoma

17 Changes in Nestin and its apparent pattern of change in expression could be induced by *in vitro* culture
18 (unpublished data and observations).
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28